

Utilization of Maternal and Child Health (MCH) Books for Pregnant Women in the Working Area of the Siulak Gedang Health Center

Nadila Zikra Wahyuni¹, M. Ridwan¹, Ismi Nurwaqiah Ibnu¹, Puspita Sari¹

Public Health Sciences Study Program, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Jambi University
Jl. Jambi - Muara Bulian No.KM. 15, Mendalo Darat, Kec. Jambi Luar Kota, Kabupaten Muaro Jambi, Jambi

Abstract:- The Maternal Mortality rates (MMR) and Infant Mortality rates (IMR) in Indonesia are still very high. This can be influenced by various factors. The MCH Handbook functions as an information tool and health screening for pregnant women, infants, and toddlers. Currently, the utilization of the MCH Handbook for pregnant women is still very low. considering that this book influences the Knowledge and Attitudes of Pregnant Women in improving their health status. The research method used is qualitative, with an analytic descriptive approach. The informants for this study consisted of pregnant women, heads of the Health Center, coordinators of the MCH Poly, Health Center midwives, Practical Midwives, and Clinical Midwives. Data collection through in-depth interviews, observation, and document review. The analytical approach used is content analysis. Qualitative data analysis using the help of Open Code software. The knowledge of pregnant women in using the MCH handbook regarding the contents, functions, benefits, and activities is good, but the understanding is still not correct. The attitude of pregnant women in using the MCH handbook is still lacking. It can be seen from the interest in reading and the lack of understanding of the contents of the MCH handbook. In addition, the role of health workers is still lacking because they have not explained the functions and contents of the MCH handbook. The knowledge of pregnant women regarding the use of the MCH handbook is good because pregnant women already understand the contents, functions, benefits, and activities of the MCH handbook. But they still don't understand the meaning of the MCH handbook. The attitude of pregnant women in utilizing the MCH handbook is still lacking because they rarely read and use the MCH handbook in an effort to prevent IMR and MMR. The role of health workers in utilizing the MCH handbook is still less visible than not conducting counseling regarding the MCH handbook to pregnant women.

Keywords;- Utilization of the MCH Handbook; Pregnant Women; Siulak Gedang Health Center.

I. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia's Crude Mortality Rate (AKK) based on National Research (RISKESDAS) in 2007 pointed to 4.6/1000 out of a total population of 973662 with the number of deaths reaching 4445. Meanwhile, the Infant Mortality Rate (IMR) showed 22/1000 and the Child Mortality Rate 41/ 1000 from all provinces in Indonesia. Jambi Province's Crude Death Rate (AKK) was found to be 3.5/1000. When compared with other provinces in Indonesia, Jambi Province is in the medium category. The Infant Mortality Rate (IMR) is 22/1000 and the Child Mortality Rate (AKA) is 40/1000 [1]. The maternal mortality rate (MMR) in Indonesia is still high. In 1991 the MMR reached 390/1000. This figure decreased in 1997 to 334/1000. The same thing happened in the following 5 years, namely in 2002 it reached 307. A decrease in the maternal mortality rate (MMR) also occurred in 2007 up to 228/100. In 2015 it decreased to 305/100 live births. The maternal mortality rate in 2019 reached 4,221 deaths per year. In 2020, MMR in Indonesia reached 4,627 deaths [2].

Meanwhile, the MMR in Jambi Province until 2020 was 96/100,000 live births over the last 7 years. The Maternal Mortality Rate (MMR) in Jambi Province from 2014 to 2019 has increased from 50-59 cases [3]. Kerinci Regency has the second largest number of MMR, namely 9 cases when compared to Regencies/Cities in Jambi Province [4].

In addition to the maternal mortality rate (MMR), the infant mortality rate (IMR) also needs to be considered together. In Indonesia, the Infant Mortality Rate (IMR) has decreased, based on data from the Directorate of Family Health in 2020 of 20,266 deaths out of 28,158 under-five deaths. Percentage 72% of total under-five deaths. Based on reports on the number of infant deaths in Jambi Province in 2019 there were 290 cases with an infant mortality rate (IMR) of 4.41 from all Regencies/Cities in Jambi Province. In line with these data, Kerinci Regency shows a high number of infant deaths after Tebo Regency [5]. This is because the capacity of health workers and the management of maternal and child health services are still not optimal in their implementation. Even though this death rate is far below the national rate, it only needs to be an evaluation and concern for the community and the government.

One of the efforts used as a means of improving maternal and child health is the MCH book. The book contains health information for mothers, from pregnancy, birth, the postpartum period, and continues to record the health of newborn babies until the child is 6 years old. This means that the MCH book is a health detection tool for pregnant women and children. The MCH book must be used properly by mothers, fathers and all other family members [6]. The use of MCH books can influence knowledge and prevent death for pregnant women. Based on research conducted by Siti Najmah in 2022, it is stated that the MCH book can be a media for information and knowledge in preventing the risk of death for pregnant women [7]. The function of the MCH book is to provide communication, information and education regarding the health of pregnant women and babies.

As in the initial observations made in the Siulak Gedang Health Center Work Area, regarding the use of MCH Books. Pregnant and breastfeeding mothers do not understand how to use the MCH book. It can be seen that there are still pregnant women who have not read and do not include the book when consulting the Community Health Center. This is in line with previous research by Sistiarani 2014, that the use of maternal and child health (MCH) books are still not optimal, this can be seen from the lack of use and ownership of MCH books for pregnant women [8]. Meanwhile, cadres of pregnant women have a role in increasing the possibility of using MCH books by 1.6 times [9]. Agreeing with Amalia, 2021 explains that midwives have not been optimal in implementing health services using MCH books [10].

The MCH book should be used as a means of communication for pregnant women and to establish good communication in improving the quality of services. There is a lack of consultation opportunities so communication between pregnant women and MCH polyclinic midwives is less than optimal. This can be seen from initial observations of MCH poly midwives and pregnant women in the Siulak Gedang Community Health Center Work Area which did not show any communication between MCH poly midwives and pregnant women. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct research on "Utilization of Maternal and Child Health Books (MCH) for Pregnant Women in the Working Area of the Siulak Gedang Health Center".

II. METODE

The type of research used in this research is qualitative research. The research approach uses descriptive analysis. This research was conducted by interviewing pregnant women, MCH polyclinic midwives, and the Head of the Siulak Gedang Community Health Center. So that from these answers you can then answer existing problems. The place where this research was carried out was at the Siulak Gedang Kerinci Community Health Center, Jambi Province. The time this research was carried out was January-July 2023. The informants in this research were pregnant women in the working area of the Siulak Gedang Health Center, Midwife Clinic and Midwife Practice in 2023.

Supporting informants were MCH Poly Midwives, Heads of Community Health Centers, Midwife Clinics and Midwife Practices. in 2023. The number of informants for the MCH Book is 1 MCH Poly Midwife Coordinator, 2 MCH Poly Midwives at the Public health center and the Head of the Siulak Gedang Community Health Center, 1 Clinical Midwife and 3 Practicing Midwives in the working area of the Siulak Gedang Community Health Center, while pregnant women are the informants. totaling 15 people in the working area of the Siulak Gedang Community Health Center. The research informant selection technique uses purposive sampling. After observations and interviews were carried out, the data was then managed using the triangulation method. This research uses data triangulation. Activities in data analysis are data reduction, presentation, and verification.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Siulak Gedang Community Health Center is one of the Community Health Centers in the Kerinci Regency, Jambi Province. The Siulak Gedang Health Center provides services in the health sector in the form of promotive, preventive, curative, and rehabilitative with a number of activities in accordance with the function of the public health center, namely as a center for driving health-oriented development, a center for community empowerment and a center for first-rate health services. In order to improve healthy living and provide comprehensive and integrated health services to the community.

This research was conducted on 15 mothers who were attending services at the Siulak Gedang Community Health Center. The following are the characteristics of the informants used:

Table 1. Characteristics of Research Informants Utilization of Maternal and Child Health (MCH) Books for Pregnant Women in the Working Area of the Siulak Gedang Health Center

Informant	Age	Level of Education	Work
IBH01	32	Senior High School	Housewife
IBH02	32	Senior High School	Housewife
IBH03	29	Bachelor Profession	Pharmacist
IBH04	29	Senior High School	Housewife
IBH05	37	Senior High School	Teacher
IBH06	29	Bachelor	Teacher
IBH07	30	Bachelor	Teacher
IBH08	30	Senior High School	Housewife
IBH09	20	Senior High School	Housewife
IBH10	28	Junior High School	Housewife
IBH11	24	Bachelor	Housewife
IBH12	26	Bachelor	Housewife
IBH13	27	Bachelor	Teacher
IBH14	28	Bachelor	Teacher
IBH15	35	Bachelor	Teacher

Based on Table 1 it is known that the informants in this study were pregnant women aged 20-35 years. In addition, most of the education levels of pregnant women entered the middle and high levels with 6 junior high schools, 8 graduates or professions, and 1 lower education level. Most of the jobs

owned by pregnant women were unemployed, totaling 8 people, namely Housewives and the rest were working with 6 teachers and 1 pharmacist. Based on the data above, it can be

seen that the respondents in this study varied from different backgrounds. The Characteristics of Informants which include Health Workers as follows:

Table 2. Characteristics of Health Worker Research Informants

Informant	Age	Level of Education	Work
KP01	42	Bachelor	Head of Public Health Center
BDK01	49	Bachelor	Midwife Coordinator of MCH Poly
BDP01	42	Bachelor	Midwife Public Health Center
BDP02	31	D3	Midwife Public Health Center
PB01	34	Bachelor	Midwife Praktek
PB02	48	D3	Practice Midwife
PB03	36	D3	Practice Midwife

The research was carried out on 3-29 May 2023 at the Siulak Gedang Community Health Center and Main Clinic. This research was carried out in 2 places, namely the Siulak Gedang Community Health Center and the Nanti Serak Main Clinic, Jambi Province. Information for this research was obtained from interviews with pregnant women and health workers (Public health center midwives, practice midwives, and heads of health centers).

➤ *Pregnant Women's Knowledge of the Use of MCH Books*

Based on the research results, it can be seen that the informants are mostly pregnant women who already know the MCH handbook. Respondents answered that the MCH book is a book that contains information about pregnancy, womb, and child care. After conducting in-depth interviews with pregnant women, it was discovered that pregnant women had insufficient knowledge of the meaning of the MCH handbook. According to pregnant women, the meaning of the MCH book is a book that discusses mothers during pregnancy. Several informants have answered correctly that the MCH Handbook is a book on maternal and child health.

"Know about the development of the fetus in the womb and the child's growth and development after birth" (IBH03, 29 years, Bachelor Profession, Pharmacist)

Results of interviews with pregnant women regarding the function of the MCH book. From the interview, the pregnant mother explained that the function of the MCH book is as a tool to find out the child's development and as a nutritional guide. Apart from that, pregnant women answered that the function of the MCH book was to find out about pregnancy complaints and about pregnancy.

"The function of this MCH handbook is, uh... we can see how... um... the development of the fetus, the development of the womb is like that" (IBH14, 28 years, Bachelor, Teacher)

Pregnant women's knowledge regarding the contents of the MCH book is generally good. This can be seen from the answers of pregnant women that the contents in the MCH book are health records either before or after pregnancy. Another informant answered that the MCH book could be a medical history tool for mothers and children. Apart from children, pregnant women also said that the MCH book contained information regarding health during childbirth.

"to check blood type, for Hb, for ee.. especially ee.. to see if we have any complaints or not, everything is filled in the book" (IBH11, 24 yrs, Bachelor, Housewife)

"What's it called, um.. medical history, patient data um..the stages of child development, then there's um..good food for mothers and children like that" (IBH13, 27 Years, Bachelor, Teacher)

The results of the study showed that most pregnant women were correct in explaining the benefits of the MCH handbook, namely as a tool to help monitor the growth and development of the baby and the dangers to the mother during pregnancy. Based on interviews, pregnant women mentioned that the MCH handbook could be used as a tool for measuring weight and height as well as immunization for children.

"Monitoring the progress of pregnancy, monitoring the completeness of maternal and child vaccines, ee... whether the child's growth and development is normal or not, such as height, head circumference and weight of the child" (IBH03, 29 years, Bachelor Profession, Pharmacist)

"Can provide information related to the health of mothers and children, one of which is how to maintain children's growth and development so that it remains good" (IBH04, 29, Senior High School, Housewife)

➤ *Attitudes of Pregnant Women towards the Use of MCH Books*

The majority of respondents did not read and used the MCH book independently. This was revealed by pregnant women that the MCH handbook was only read when it was handed over to the midwife to fill it out. This means that pregnant women are less motivated to diligently read MCH books. Of all the informants interviewed, the majority answered that they had read the MCH book. However, the reading intensity is low. In fact, quite a few have read just one MCH book.

"no ah, "yes, never, nothing, because there was nothing in my opinion so I didn't read it" (IBH05, 37 yrs, high school, teacher)

"I did, but I wasn't very diligent" (IBH07, 30 years old, Bachelor, teacher)

The obstacles experienced by pregnant women are because they are busy. Busy with home matters and other jobs such as teacher and pharmacist.

"Sometimes I don't have time, because sometimes there's a lot of homework, right" (IBH07, 30 years old, Bachelor, Teacher)

This research also looked at the extent to which pregnant women brought MCH books to health services (Integrated Healthcare Centers, Community Health Centers, or Clinic). Data from interviews obtained that all pregnant women carried an MCH book when consulting with a Midwife or Health Officer.

"Yes there is, there is no book, people don't want to check it" (IBH02, 32 years old, Senior High School, Housewife)

Based on the research results, it can be found that pregnant women respondents do not know clearly about IMR and AKI. So efforts have not been made to prevent infant mortality and maternal mortality. However, there are still many pregnant women who have not implemented AKB and AKI because they do not know about this.

"Um...for mothers, by eating nutritious food, maintaining weight ee..even though every girl wants to be skinny all but pregnant women don't want to be thin, let the body get fat first right (IBH13, 27 yrs, Bachelor, Teacher)

From the interview results, there were pregnant women who answered that they had carried out activities to prevent MMR and IMR, namely by means of nutritious food according to the recommended 4 Healthy 5 Perfect. And always keep food clean and healthy. Next, do light exercise regularly, such as gymnastics or walking. Immunization or vaccine is also important as a simple step in efforts to prevent or reduce IMR and MMR in Indonesia. MCH books play an important role as home-based tools to ensure sustainable maternal and child health.

"Yes, it's effective, because in the book you can say that it's complete, right? Information about maternal and child health... so it can be used for guidelines on maternal and child health. There is also a check column for each pregnant woman taking blood-boosting vitamins. do you know if you drink or not" (PB03, 36 years old, D3)

➤ *The Health Workers in Utilizing the MCH Handbook*

Based on the results of interviews conducted with pregnant women, health checks were carried out during visits to the Community Health Center or Integrated Healthcare Center. During pregnancy, there are several examinations carried out by health workers on pregnant women. These activities include ultrasound examination, measuring LILA, checking heart rate, measuring blood pressure and weighing pregnant women. Apart from that, pregnant women also measure the uterine fundus.

"ee..examination ee..just check ee..tension, right, then check ee..growth and development ee..the baby's growth and development is mostly done by measuring what kind of fluid it is, ee..after that, check the fetal heart rate, and now there are more ultrasounds at health centers, even though two-dimensional ultrasound is an ultrasound test, sometimes with a doctor (IBH13, 27 years, Bachelor, teacher)

"Usually it's sneezed ee... if you're pregnant, it's checked ee... what kind of equipment do you use ee... to see if the baby's heartbeat is active inside or not, whether it's healthy or not. "If the child is too big in the womb, we are told to eat less" (IBH07, 30 years, Bachelor, Teacher)

The role of health workers is good in providing services. Midwives always carry out examinations well and provide medication according to pregnant women's complaints.

The research results showed that the majority of pregnant women answered that health workers did not provide information and explanations regarding the function, benefits, contents, and how to fill out the MCH book.

"By providing counseling, carrying out examinations... carrying out curative measures if for example there is something that needs to be treated" (IBH03, 29 years, Bachelor Profession, Pharmacist)

"Ee..as long as this book is, yes, many of them don't understand so they just fill in this if it's an old book ee..yes the service is good" (IBH12, 26 years, Bachelor, Housewife)

Based on all the variables above, it can be concluded that the role of health workers in carrying out examinations is good. By doing an inspection. However, midwives have not socialized or explained the MCH book to pregnant women.

The MCH book is a notebook used with the aim of improving maintenance or health care for mothers and children and improving the quality of MCH services. Utilization of the MCH handbook is not only for health workers but also for pregnant women. The utilization is based on the results of interviews that there is still a lack of use of the MCH handbook in daily life.

Utilization of the MCH handbook The indicator of observation is ownership of the MCH handbook. Based on the results of interviews with pregnant women, all informants already had MCH books. Ownership of the book from the pregnancy of the first child was given by the Siluak Gedang Health Center. This is supported by the statement of Sistiarani et al 2014 that the use of maternal and child health books can be observed from the ownership of the MCH book. This means that it is mandatory for every pregnant woman to have a MCH book [8].

Utilization of the MCH handbook is said to be effective if the mother has read, understood and applied the contents of the MCH handbook. The availability of MCH books at Community Health Centers is sufficient and facilitates pregnant women in obtaining health facilities. Based on the results of interviews, pregnant women still do not bring MCH

books to the Public health center. Based on what the Midwife and Head of the Community Health Center said, it is mandatory for pregnant women to always bring the MCH book to the Community Health Center and Integrated Healthcare Center. The results of this research are in line with research conducted by Mariyana in 2019 which explained that mothers' compliance with carrying MCH books was still lacking. This lack of compliance is caused by, among other things, age, low education level, employment level and lack of understanding of the mother [11].

Many pregnant women are still lazy about reading MCH books, this is because they are busy at home or work. If we look at the benefits of the MCH book for pregnant women, it is very large, so it can help mothers and families in preventing health problems. In this case, it is supported by research conducted by Herfanda and Subiyatun in 2021 which explains that pregnant women use the MCH book as a form of preparation for pregnant women in childbirth [12]. Apart from that, research conducted by Karminingsih in 2021 explained that pregnant women respondents had made good use of the MCH book [13].

All pregnant women in the Siluak Gedang work area have a MCH book. This means that the Community Health Center and the Government have provided good facilities to pregnant women, one of which is the availability of MCH books. However, the availability of these facilities is not matched by an increase in pregnant women's interest in reading MCH books. This is in line with research conducted by Effendi 2020 that the distribution of MCH books has been evenly distributed in all health centers and midwives in the district. East Belitung, Batu City and Kab. Cianjur [14].

The MCH handbook is used by pregnant women as additional information on pregnancy health. What pregnant women must read in the MCH handbook is about rest patterns. In addition, physical activity for pregnant women, preparation for childbirth, a balanced nutritional menu pattern that must be consumed daily to meet the needs of both the mother and the fetus during pregnancy, preventing anemia, and preparing for lactation, understanding how to maintain cleanliness to prevent infection, recognizing and understanding signs the dangers of pregnancy so that mothers can detect the dangers of pregnancy as early as possible and prevent the risk of pregnancy. This is supported by a statement from Napitupulu et al 2018 that in the MCH handbook, there is information that provides knowledge of the danger signs experienced by pregnant women [15].

Health workers are one of the main components in providing health services for pregnant women. From the results of interviews with pregnant women, so far health workers or midwives have provided good service. Although it is still not optimal in providing consultations or health promotion regarding MCH books. In this study, pregnant women did not receive support from health workers in using MCH books.

Health officers are required to explain the meaning of the MCH Book. The role of health workers must also explain the benefits of the MCH Book. Pregnant women need to be accompanied by a midwife or health worker when filling out the MCH book. This is supported by technical instructions from the Ministry of Health that the task of health workers is to assist cadres, mothers, and families in understanding the contents of the book, filling it out, and making optimal use of it to get higher quality services [4].

Apart from that, health workers need to explain the health programs in the MCH book. So the task of health workers is not only to prescribe drugs but also to provide information and education (IEC) to pregnant women about the MCH handbook and how to fill out the book. In line with this research, Karwati et al in 2021 explained that counseling conducted by midwives must use MCH books in order to increase the knowledge of pregnant women [16].

Based on observations at the Public health center, all of the 3 midwives provided explanations about the contents of the MCH handbook to pregnant women. In contrast to the statement by the health center midwife who explained the contents of the MCH handbook after conducting a health screening. This lack of support could be caused by the lack of counseling skills of health workers in providing information on MCH books to pregnant women. These results are in line with research conducted by Bonita et al 2020 which obtained the influence of midwives' attitudes towards the use of MCH books with a percentage of 75% in the poor category [17].

Therefore, the role of health workers or midwives must always be to motivate pregnant women to read MCH books independently at home. In addition, midwives at Public health centers and clinics midwives should be reminded to always bring their MCH books to health care facilities. This agrees with research presented by Fitriyaningsih 2021 that health workers play a major role in contributing to the effective use of MCH books by pregnant women [18].

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion above, several things can be concluded that the knowledge of pregnant women regarding the use of the MCH handbook is good because pregnant women already understand the contents, functions, benefits, and activities of using the MCH handbook. But I still don't understand the meaning of the KIA book. The attitude of pregnant women regarding the use of MCH books is still lacking because they rarely read and use MCH books in an effort to prevent IMR and AKI. The role of health workers in the use of MCH books is still less visible than not providing counseling regarding KIA books to pregnant women.

REFERENCES

- [1]. J. Irianto, M. Anwar, and W. Yuwana, "Angka Kematian di Berbagai Provinsi di Indonesia (Data RISKESDAS 2007)," *J. Ekol. Kesehat.*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 1047–1056, 2009.
- [2]. Kemenkes RI, *Profil Kesehatan Indonesia 2019*. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://pusdatin.kemkes.go.id/resources/download/pusdatin/profil-kesehatan-indonesia/Profil-Kesehatan-indonesia-2019.pdf>
- [3]. Kementerian Kesehatan RI, "Laporan RISKESDAS Provinsi Jambi Tahun 2018," Jakarta, 2019.
- [4]. Kemenkes RI, *Buku KIA Kesehatan Ibu dan Anak*. 2020.
- [5]. Pemerintah Daerah Provinsi Jambi, *Profil Kesehatan 2019*. Jambi: Dinas Kesehatan Provinsi Jambi, 2020.
- [6]. C. Sistiarani, E. Gamelia, and D. U. P. Sari, "Fungsi Pemanfaatan Buku KIA terhadap Pengetahuan Kesehatan Ibu dan Anak pada Ibu," *Kesmas Natl. Public Heal. J.*, vol. 8, no. 8, p. 353, 2014, doi: 10.21109/kesmas.v8i8.404.
- [7]. N. Siti, Suryani, and Imelda, "Efektivitas Edukasi Kesehatan Dengan Buku Kia Dan Media Elektronik Terhadap Deteksi Dini Kehamilan Risiko Tinggi Pada Ibu Hamil," *J. Nurs. Updat.*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 60–67, 2022.
- [8]. C. Sistiarani, E. Gamelia, and D. U. P. Sari, "Fungsi Pemanfaatan Buku KIA terhadap Pengetahuan Kesehatan Ibu dan Anak pada Ibu," *Kesmas Natl. Public Heal. J.*, vol. 8, no. 8, 2014, doi: 10.21109/kesmas.v8i8.404.
- [9]. E. R. Wijhati, "Peningkatan Kapasitas Kader Dalam Pemanfaatan Buku Kesehatan Ibu dan Anak (KIA)," *Abdi Geomedisains*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 130–138, 2022, doi: 10.23917/abdiomedisains.v2i2.326.
- [10]. R. Amalia, "Optimalisasi Peran Bidan Dalam Pemanfaatan Buku KIA," *J. Vokasi Kesehat.*, vol. 6, no. 2, 2021, doi: 10.30602/jvk.v6i2.551.
- [11]. Mariyana, "Kepatuhan Ibu Membawa Buku Kesehatan Ibu dan Anak," *J. Darul Azhar*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 59–67, 2019, [Online]. Available: http://repository.radenintan.ac.id/11375/1/PERPUS_PUSAT.pdf%0Ahttp://business-law.binus.ac.id/2015/10/08/pariwisata-syariah/%0Ahttps://www.ptonline.com/articles/how-to-get-better-mfi-results%0Ahttps://journal.uir.ac.id/index.php/kiat/article/view/8839
- [12]. E. Herfanda and S. Subiyatun, "Gambaran pemanfaatan buku kesehatan ibu dan anak (KIA) oleh ibu hamil trimester iii tentang persiapan persalinan di Puskesmas Tempel 1," *J. Kebidanan*, vol. 10, no. 2, p. 129, 2021, doi: 10.26714/jk.10.2.2021.129-140.
- [13]. Karminingsih, Latifah, and F. A. Saputri, "Gambaran Pengetahuan Ibu Tentang Pemanfaatan Buku Kesehatan Ibu Dan," *J. Kesmas Prima Indones.*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 1–6, 2021.
- [14]. D. E. Effendi, A. P. Nugroho, S. Suharmiati, and L. Handayani, "Analisis Kebutuhan dan Pemanfaatan Buku Serta Pedoman Pelayanan KIA di Puskesmas: Studi Kualitatif," *Bul. Penelit. Sist. Kesehat.*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 99–107, 2020, doi: 10.22435/hsr.v23i2.3086.
- [15]. T. F. Napitupulu, L. Rahmiati, D. S. Handayani, E. P. Setiawati, and A. I. Susanti, "Gambaran Pemanfaatan Buku KIA dan Pengetahuan Ibu Hamil Mengenai Tanda Bahaya Kehamilan," *J. Kesehat. Vokasional*, vol. 3, no. 1, p. 17, 2018, doi: 10.22146/jkesvo.33900.
- [16]. F. N. Annisa, "The Relationship Between Reading Interest Of Kia Book With Pregnant Mothers Knowledge About Kia Book," *J. Promkes*, vol. 4 (2), pp. 188–198, 2016, [Online]. Available: <https://e-journal.unair.ac.id/PROMKES/article/view/7650/4527>
- [17]. F. Amal and S. Dondi, "Rendahnya Minat Membaca Buku KIA Pada Ibu Gravida di Puskesmas Abepura Kota Jayapura Tahun 2018," *Gema Kesehat.*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 49–54, 2018, [Online]. Available: <http://garuda.ristekbrin.go.id/documents/detail/1267608>
- [18]. Fitriyaningsih, "Determinan pemanfaatan buku kesehatan ibu dan anak (kia) pada ibu hamil dan balita di wilayah kerja puskesmas eban tahun 2021," *J. Kebidanan dan Keperawatan*, vol. 03, no. 01, pp. 35–40, 2021.